

Spectral regression analysis of solvent parameters on azo-derivatives of 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylo)-6-aminouracil and estimation of change in dipole moment from ground to excited state

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Abstract : The electronic absorption maxima (ν_{\max}) of azo-uracil derivatives of 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylo)-6-aminouracil (aryl = $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$ (1), $-\text{p-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ (2), $-\text{p-ClC}_6\text{H}_4$ (3), $-\text{p-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ (4)) are susceptible to bathochromic/hypsochromic shift depending on organic solvents used for the study. The effects of different solvent parameters such as *E*, *M*, *N*, *K*, *J* and *H* expressed by either dielectric constant or refractive index or both on the electronic absorption spectra have thus been studied by linear multiple regression analysis (LMRA) in order to evaluate the solvent-solute interactions of these dyes in various organic solvents. The relative values of multiple correlation coefficient (MCC) resulted from LMRA of ν_{\max} versus different solvent parameters for the dyes 1-3 indicate that permanent dipole (dyes)-dipole (solvents) and H-bonding interactions between the molecules of solute (dye)-solvent in a particular solvent are the noteworthy interactions for shifting ν_{\max} values. However, for the dye 4 dipole-dipole interaction plays predominant role in shifting ν_{\max} . Besides, the analysis of Kamlet-Taft parameters on the electronic absorption spectra and Lippert-Mataga and Reichardt-Ravi plots on Stokes shift also evidence the role of H-bonding (both HBA and HBD) and dipolar interactions in hypsochromic/bathochromic shift of ν_{\max} for the dyes 1-4. The change in dipole moment ($\Delta\mu$) resulted from Intramolecular Charge Transfer (ICT) transitions in the excited state were calculated for the dyes 1-3 using Lippert-Mataga and Reichardt-Ravi equations that results in the order : Dye-2 > Dye-3 > Dye-1.

Keywords : Arylo-uracil, solvent parameters, LMRA, Kamlet-Taft parameters, dipole moments.

Introduction

Uracil derivatives which have pyrimidine-like structures (uracil = pyrimidine-2,4-dione) have extremely found applications in medicine and biology^{1,2}. Pyrimidine dyes in some cases, prepared from 6-aminouracils have been used in preparation of hypnotic drugs³ and in detecting cancer⁴, proving their pharmacological and biological activities⁵. For instances, 3-aminoisothiazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrimidine-4,6-diones which are of use as sedative, inflammation and adenosine 3,5-cyclophosphate phosphodiesterase inhibitor⁶ are prepared from 6-amino-1,3-dimethyluracil. Nevertheless, the azo derivatives of uracil have been given attention very recently^{7,8}.

Presumably, potential uses of a solute for a particular field of science such as biology, chemistry or physics are considerably influenced by its surroundings i.e. solvent(s). Solvation plays a crucial role in various processes taking place in the liquid phase. Many biological processes in-

cluding transportation, signaling, metabolism are also controlled by solvation^{9,10}. It influences reaction rates, equilibria, and mechanisms for many compounds as well¹¹. And solvation of a solute depends solely on the interactions present in between a solute and a solvent in a solution. Thus, it is indeed important and demanding to point out by investigating different types of solute-solvent interactions in solution which affect solvation process of a solute. The solute-solvent interactions are categorized as specific (acid-base, hydrogen bonding) and non-specific (dipolar/polarizable) in nature. Solvent parameters mainly dielectric constant and refractive index are involved in representing various solvent properties and functions¹².

The UV-Vis and fluorescence spectroscopies are the two inevitable tools to study the solvation effects upon a solute. The shifts of absorption, excitation and emission maxima in either ways (bathochromic or hypsochromic) are supposed to be considered as the result of solute-sol-

vent interactions. The observed shifts of electronic absorption bands of solute molecules induced by solvents are commonly understood as an indication of the extent of charge reorganization of solute molecules upon electronic excitation¹³.

Recently, we have published a paper on azo-derivatives of 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylo)-6-aminouracil⁸. From the electronic absorption spectra it had been demonstrated that the hydrazone tautomer is the predominant form present in solution and the hydrogen bonding parameter of solvents plays important role in shifting its λ_{\max} towards blue. In this paper we thus report a systematic study of effects of different solvent parameters expressed by either dielectric constant or refractive index or both and of Kamlet-Taft parameters on azo-derivatives of 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylo)-6-aminouracil (**1-4**, Scheme 1) by following linear multiple regression analysis (LMRA) technique in order to evaluate specific and non-specific solute-solvent interaction effects on the electronic absorption/emission spectra of the dyes. Besides, an attempt was taken to estimate their changes in dipole moments from ground to excited states and the subsequent results are also reported herewith. Determination of changes in dipole moments ($\Delta\mu$) of these dye molecules is significant because such values of solutes may provide valuable information about the change in electronic distribution upon excitation which is quite useful in designing nonlinear materials¹⁴, in elucidation of the nature of the excited states and also it reflects the charge distribution in the molecule upon excitation.

Scheme 1. Chemical structure of derivatives 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylo)-6-aminouracil (**1-4**).

Results and discussion

UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy :

The absorption spectra in few more solvents were recorded in this study and along with reported solvents spectral data⁸ for all the dyes **1-4** under study are listed in

Table 1. The dyes **1-3** show almost similar one well defined band in the range of 25000–27778 cm^{-1} along with a shoulder band at 23810–25000 cm^{-1} whereas the dye **4** exhibits the same band at 20000–25000 cm^{-1} . In earlier communication observing the position of ν_{\max} in different organic solvents we have demonstrated that the dyes under study (**1-4**) exhibit a protonated hydrazone and deprotonated hydrazone anion equilibrium in solution, as shown in Scheme 2. Absorption spectra for the dyes **1-3** and the dye **4** in selected solvents are given in Figs. S1 and S2, respectively (Supplementary materials). However, to get quantitative evidences the effects of solvent parameters on azo dyes a LMRA of the obtained ν_{\max} values of the dyes with solvent polarity parameters were studied and discussed in the following section.

LMRA : Effect of solvent-solute parameters :

Dissolution of a solute in a particular solvent results various kind of solute-solvent interactions such as solute-solvent hydrogen bonding, dipolar interactions, etc. which depend not only on different solvent polarity parameters but also polarity of the solute molecule. Electronic absorption maxima are susceptible to get a shift either way (bathochromic or hypsochromic) in a solvent compared to other solvents depending specifically on the extent of such interactions. Several one-, two- and three-parameter equations have been used for the careful combination of different solvent parameters, E , K , M , N , J and H for the different solvents used under study to correlate with spectral shifts at ν_{\max} by using the LMRA technique with eq. (1) as illustrated in Experimental section. Each of the solvent parameter used (Table S1) may have certain contribution to each of the various interaction mechanisms present between solute-solvent molecules in solution. The results of regression analysis are given in Tables S4-S11 (Supplementary data). The multiple correlation coefficients (MCC) for the dyes under study have been drafted from S4-S11 and given in Table 2. The MCC value is considered as a measure of the goodness of the fit. The high value of MCC (near one) means that a certain solvent parameter has a good correlation to the spectral shifts. In other words, the spectral shifts for the peak are greatly sensitive to the solvent parameter that gives a value of MCC near to unity. Alternatively, the small value (near zero) of the significance parameter (P) (S4-S11) means the correlation is good.

Table 1. Absorption and emission maxima wave numbers and Stokes shift (in cm^{-1}) for the dyes **1-4** in different solvents

Solvents	Dye 1			Dye 2			Dye 3			Dye 4		
	ν_{abs}	ν_{flu}	$\nu_{\text{abs}} - \nu_{\text{flu}}$									
Hex ^a	25907	23041	2866	25381	22676	2705	26110	23310	2800	25253	22883	2370
CHCl_3^a	25641	22831	2810	25063	22831	2232	25907	22831	3076	24938	22831	2107
DCM^a	27100	23041	4059	26810	22413	4397	26525	22222	4303	25000	22214	2786
EA	27473	23256	4217	27100	22936	4164	26882	22831	4051	25063	20661	4402
2-Propanol	27624	23256	4368	27473	23041	4432	27027	22936	4091	25253	21552	3701
Acetone	27473	24752	2721	27248	22573	4675	26882	22075	4807	24570	20325	4245
EtOH^a	27701	23148	4553	27473	22883	4590	27027	22727	4300	25189	20618	4571
MeOH^a	27778	23041	4737	27548	22989	4559	27174	22831	4343	25189	21645	3544
AN	27472	22832	4640	27322	22989	4333	26954	22624	4330	24814	20284	4530
DMF^a	27322	23148	4174	27027	23148	3879	26882	23148	3734	23256	19881	3375
DMSO^a	27174	22831	4343	26882	22727	4155	26738	22831	3907	22779	19646	3133

^aData adopted from the Ref. 8.**Scheme 2.** Azo-hydrazone equilibrium ($\text{A} \leftrightarrow \text{B}$), HBD solvated hydrazone-anion form (C), HBA (DMSO) solvated hydrazone-anion form (D) of 1,3-dimethyl-5-(arylaazo)-6-aminouracil (**1-4**).

The MCC values as listed in Table 2 obtained from one parameter equations for E , M , N and K reveal that these parameters exert their influence on spectral shift on ν_{max} for the dyes **1-3** with an order $N > K > E \gg M$ whereas the parameter M on ν_{max} for the dye **4** (order of MCC value : $M \gg N, K; E = 0$). This means that the solute permanent dipole-solvent induced dipole interactions that depends on the solvent refractive index (parameter M) has negligible effect on solvatochromism for the

dyes **1-3** whereas it is the predominating parameter for the dye **4**. For the dyes **1-3** it can thus be demonstrated that the solute permanent dipole-solvent permanent dipole interactions (N) and solvent polarity (E , K) those mainly depend on dielectric interactions (ϵ) and hydrogen bonding abilities (HBD and HBA) of the solvents, are the major guiding factors for affecting solvatochromism. The correlation data of the two-parameter equations with the solvent spectral shifts showed better fit to these spectral

Table 2. The multiple correlation coefficient (MCC) for the dyes 1-4

Parameter	MCC values			
	Dye 1	Dye 2	Dye 3	Dye 4
<i>E</i>	0.591	0.687	0.611	0.0
<i>M</i>	0.248	0.205	0.281	0.500
<i>N</i>	0.756	0.833	0.723	0.115
<i>K</i>	0.661	0.787	0.614	0.141
<i>E, M</i>	0.653	0.719	0.688	0.562
<i>E, N</i>	0.760	0.845	0.737	0.420
<i>E, K</i>	0.693	0.819	0.673	0.446
<i>M, N</i>	0.874	0.917	0.866	0.728
<i>M, K</i>	0.852	0.937	0.837	0.684
<i>N, K</i>	0.815	0.837	0.813	0.171
<i>E, M, N</i>	0.878	0.917	0.867	0.814
<i>E, M, K</i>	0.854	0.937	0.837	0.731
<i>E, N, K</i>	0.816	0.947	0.819	0.448
<i>M, N, K</i>	0.875	0.938	0.874	0.825
<i>J</i>	0.697	0.777	0.658	0.175
<i>H</i>	0.172	0.147	0.192	0.579
<i>E, J</i>	0.719	0.811	0.699	0.553
<i>E, H</i>	0.625	0.704	0.652	0.637
<i>J, H</i>	0.856	0.911	0.836	0.767
<i>J, N</i>	0.844	0.901	0.837	0.749
<i>H, N</i>	0.856	0.911	0.839	0.764
<i>E, J, H</i>	0.861	0.912	0.837	0.830
<i>E, J, N</i>	0.847	0.901	0.837	0.820
<i>E, H, N</i>	0.861	0.911	0.840	0.826
<i>J, H, N</i>	0.856	0.912	0.841	0.773

shifts than the corresponding one-parameter fits. The solvent ability to form hydrogen bond with the solute molecules, which is reflected by the parameter *E* when combined with the previously mentioned parameters *K*, *M* or *N*, is the reason for improving the correlations. For instance when the parameter *E* is combined with the parameters *M* (dye 1) the MCC value jumped to 0.653. It is also clear that three parameter equations give better fit to the spectral shift (higher MCC values) than two-parameter equation; the data show an improvement in the fit in later case compared with the one-parameter correlation.

The MCC values obtained from one parameter equations for *J* and *H* are important to account for non-specific solute-solvent interactions such as dispersion and dipolar effects. The data as listed in Table 2 reveal that the spectral shift on ν_{\max} of the dyes 1-3 depend predominantly on *J*, the parameter which is derived from dielectric con-

stant (ϵ) and not for on *H*, the parameter which is derived from refractive index (*n*). The reverse phenomenon observes for the dye 4, where the refractive index of the solvent becomes important and higher dependence on *H* was obtained. The MCC values for the two parameter equations for *J* and *H* have considerable higher in magnitude, indicating that *H* has also some short of contribution on solvatochromism for the dyes 1-3 and *J* for the dye 4.

Thus, it may be concluded from the above discussion that not a single parameter can explain solute-solvent interaction mechanisms completely rather a combined effect of all the parameters. The relative values of MCC of one parameter equations for *E*, *M*, *N*, *K*, *J* and *H* for the dyes 1-3 clearly indicate that permanent dipole (dyes)-dipole (solvents) and hydrogen bonding interactions between solute (dye)-solvent are the noteworthy interactions for shifting ν_{\max} . Such interactions depend on the dielectric constants (ϵ) and empirical solvent polarity parameters (*E*) of the solvents used for studies. It is already mentioned that *E* factors H-bonding and dipolar interactions. The significant value of MCC of *K* (derived from ϵ) for a particular dye is accounted for dipolar interactions. The significant MCC value of *N* also suggests the dipole-dipole interactions. Thus, solute-solvent interactions present in solution for the dyes 1-3 are in the forms of dipolar-dipolar and H-bonding interactions which are responsible for shifting ν_{\max} . However, for the dye 4 dipole-dipole interaction plays predominant role in shifting ν_{\max} . This result of regression analysis of solvent polarity parameters is very much consistent with the UV-Vis spectroscopic data (Table 1).

Kamlet-Taft equation :

The effect of Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic parameters (Table S2) on the dyes 1-4 in organic solvents was analyzed using eq. (2) (Experimental section). The resulted correlation coefficients *a*, *b*, and *s* along with ν_0 are given in Table 3. The intercept ν_0 , and coefficients *a*, *b*, and *s* are independent constants and their magnitudes and sign enlightens the corresponding solute-solvent interactions¹⁵⁻¹⁸. The LMRA for the eq. (2) for the solvents excluding DCM gives the positive values of all the three coefficients (Table 3) for the dyes 1-3. The positive values of coefficients 'a' and 'b' for the dyes 1-3 indicate that H-bonding interaction between solute-solvents in solvents with both a (HBD) acidity and β (HBA) basicity plays an important role in

Table 3. Solvent independent correlation coefficients a , b , s of the Kamlet-Taft parameters for the dyes **1-4**

Dye	ν_0	a	b	s	MCC	No. of solvents
Dye 1	25903	272	1825	374	0.701	10 ^a
	27593	569	-567	74	0.95	8 ^b
Dye 2	25582	650	1098	987	0.75	10 ^a
	27455	662	-773	87	0.862	8 ^b
Dye 3	26109	169	1011	126	0.698	10 ^a
	26890	388	-296	134	0.898	8 ^b
Dye 4	25999	2602	-3017	-1483	0.60	10 ^a
	31354	1625	-5881	-58866	0.846	8 ^b

^aSolvents excluding DCM. ^bSolvents excluding Hex, CHCl₃ and DCM.

shifting ν_{\max} values of these dyes towards the hypsochromic end (Fig. S1). The hypsochromic shifting implies for stabilization of the ground state through hydrogen bonding relative to the excited state. The positive values of ' s ' of dyes **1-3** reveal that the hypsochromic shift of wave numbers are also influenced by the solvent dipolarity/polarizability parameters. As we have seen for these three dyes in their UV-Vis spectral data that the ν_{\max} values in HBA and HBD solvents shift towards hypsochromic end in respect of non-polar solvents, Hex and CHCl₃. This result is also consistent with the result obtained in the foregoing section for the dyes **1-3**. However, excluding Hex and CHCl₃ solvents the LMRA for the eq. (2) for these three dyes the coefficients ' a ' and ' s ' are positive whereas ' b ' is negative (Table 3). The results indicate that the ν_{\max} values of these three dyes shift towards hypsochromic end for HBD solvents and towards bathochromic end for HBA solvents, as observed in their UV-Vis spectral data (Table 1, Fig. S1 for MeOH and DMSO). In contrast, for the dye **4** either considering or not considering Hex and CHCl₃ solvents, in both cases the negative values of the coefficients ' b ' and ' s ' indicate that both β (HBA) and π^* (polarizability) parameters of the solvents play significant role in bathochromic shifting of ν_{\max} . Thus, the solute-solvent interactions in the excited state through hydrogen bonding and dipole-dipole interactions stabilizes the excited state, resulting bathochromic shifts as it is observed the UV-Vis spectra of the dye **4** (Fig. S2 for DMSO). In consistent with the result of UV-Vis data and LMRA of solvent parameters, the result of Kamlet-Taft parameters too evidences the role of hydrogen bonding (both HBA and HBD) and dipolar interactions in hypsochromic/bathochromic shift of ν_{\max} for the dyes **1-4**.

Estimation of change in dipole moments ($\Delta\mu$) from ground to excited states :

The emission spectra of all the dyes **1-4** obtained by excitation at their corresponding absorption wavelengths had been demonstrated as that due to the presence of strong H-bonding interaction between deprotonated hydrazone anion-solvent (alcohols) show low intense fluorescent peak in alcoholic solvents. To get concrete evidence for the origin of their emission bands, their emission and excitation spectra were recorded at varying excitation and emission wavelengths, respectively. The dyes exhibit excitation peaks different from that of the absorption peak while allowing emissions at any of their emission wavelengths (graph not included); however, their emission peaks are similar either allowing excitation at their excitation or absorption wavelengths. Their emission spectra were thus recorded in different solvents at a fixed excitation wavelength ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 355$ nm) which is lower wavelength than that of absorption λ_{max} exhibited by the dyes in any of the solvents chosen under study. Emission spectra for the dyes **1** and **4** are given in Figs. 1 and 2. This result reveals that the emission peaks of these dyes are originated from their locally excited states (LE) structure emissions. From the spectra it is clear that the dyes exhibit high intense fine structure emission in non-polar solvents (e.g. Hex) and it becomes low intense structureless in polar solvents (e.g. MeOH). In addition, a longer wavelength band (~ 550 nm) is observed in polar solvents which can be attributed to the presence of an intra-molecular charge-transfer (ICT) excited state generated by a transition from the lone-pair located on nitrogen atoms to a π^* aryl orbital (Scheme 3)¹⁹. The formation of ICT emission indicates

Fig. 1. Emission spectra of dye **1** in different solvents at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 355$ nm, circle part indicates ICT emission. Insert shows low intense emission spectra.

Fig. 2. Emission spectra of dye **4** in different solvents at $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 355$ nm; circle part indicates ICT emission. Insert shows low intense emission spectra.

Scheme 3. Schematic representation of Intramolecular Charge Transfer (ICT) in excited state of the dyes **1-4**.

that the electron distribution in the excited state for the dyes can be different than that in the ground state. Moreover, the intensity of structure emission peaks in polar solvents especially in HBD solvents is quite low (Fig. 1 insert) for the dyes **1-3**, indicating that it may be due to the strong ground state solute-solvent interaction through H-bonding (as shown in Scheme 2). Such specific solvent-solute interaction in the ground state can be evidenced by studying the polar additive (i.e. MeOH) effect on the absorption spectrum of a dye in non-polar solvent (CHCl_3 or DCM). In case of dye **2** the absorption spectrum in hexane showed loss of vibrational structure and a blue shift upon adding methanol, as shown in Fig. 3. It is noteworthy to mention that such type of polar additive effect didn't observe on emission spectra, ruling out the excited state specific solvent-solute interactions. For the dye **4**, barring non-polar solvents the low intense emission peaks are observed in all HBD and HBA solvents.

The magnitude of stokes shift as listed in Table 1 indicates that the electronic structure of the dyes in excited state may be somewhat different from that of the ground state. In order to get evidences for specific and non-specific interactions between solute-solvent molecules, the

Fig. 3. Polar additive solvent MeOH effect on absorption spectrum of dye **2** in hexane. The concentration of MeOH ranges from 0.112 mM to 11.2 mM.

spectral stokes shift in respect of their responses on Lippert-Mataga and Reichardt-Ravi plots of linearity, respectively were analyzed and given in Figs. 4-7 for the dyes **1-3**, respectively. In addition, the change in dipole moment of all the dyes was calculated using eqs. (4) and (6). In Lippert-Mataga expression, it is the plot of stokes shift vs orientation polarizability ($\Delta\mu$, eq. (3)). Representative Lippert-Mataga plots for the dyes in some selective solvents are shown in Figs. 4A-7A. At the higher end of the plot a cluster of stokes shifts are found for HBD and HBA solvents together; where stokes shifts for HBD solvents are rather greater in magnitude than for HBA solvents. However, the correlation coefficients lie in the range 0.72-0.88 for the dyes **1-3** and ~ 0.50 for the dye **4**. This result can be regarded as evidence for the contribution of specific solvent effects along with general non-specific solvent effects in the spectral shift for the dyes **1-3**. But for the dye **4**, the lower magnitude of correlation coefficient may suggest that in addition to the specific and non-specific interaction, the refractive index may play an important role in the spectra shift; the result is consistent with LMRA results. The slopes of the Lippert-Mataga plots were thereafter used for calculating change in dipole moment ($\Delta\mu = \mu_E - \mu_G$) from ground state (μ_G) to excited state (μ_E). The slope (S_{LM}), correlation coefficient and calculated change in dipole moment ($\Delta\mu$) from the slopes are given in Table 4. The $\Delta\mu$ for the dyes is moderate (ranges 6.1-7.2 D), indicating that the charge shift, i.e. ICT (Scheme 3) is predominantly depends on solvent polarity.

To get the specific interaction especially, hydrogen bonding interaction on charge shift (Scheme 3), the $\Delta\mu$

Fig. 4. Plots of polarity equations : (A) Lippert-Mataga and (B) Reichardt-Ravi for dye 1.

Fig. 5. Plots of polarity equations : (A) Lippert-Mataga and (B) Reichardt-Ravi for dye 2.

Fig. 6. Plots of polarity equations : (A) Lippert-Mataga and (B) Reichardt-Ravi for dye 3.

Fig. 7. Plots of polarity equations : (A) Lippert-Mataga and (B) Reichardt-Ravi for dye 4.

Table 4. Correlation of the spectral shifts and $\Delta\mu$ values in Debye (D) units of the dyes 1-4

Equations	Dye 1			Dye 2			Dye 3			Dye 4		
	Slope	R^2	$\Delta\mu$ (D)									
Lippert-Mataga eqn.	6475	0.883	6.84	7163	0.7178	7.19	5218	0.8789	6.14	6438	0.5885	6.82
Reichart-Ravi eq.	2652	0.8479	2.40	3251	0.7183	2.66	2322	0.8453	2.25D	2693	0.5002	2.42

were also calculated from the Reichart-Ravi plots, as shown in Figs. 4B-7B. Critically observation of Reichart-Ravi plots for the dyes it shows more close points along the lines which might be somewhat more specific interactions between solute-solvents than that of non-specific interactions. The correlation coefficient values for Reichart-Ravi plots follow the same trend as Lippert-Mataga plots for the all dyes.

Table 4 shows that barring dye 4 due to poor correlation coefficient values for the plots, the calculated $\Delta\mu$ values change as expected, in the order, Dye-2 > Dye-3 > Dye-1. The calculated $\Delta\mu$ values for the dyes obtained by Reichart-Ravi method (Table 4) are less than the Lippert-Mataga method. This is because the Lippert-Mataga method does not consider the polarizability and hydrogen bonding effect. On the other hand the Reichardt-Ravi (E_T^N) function is not only included solvent polarity but also the hydrogen bonding effect. Nevertheless, the $\Delta\mu$ values obtained in this method follow the same order as for. Moreover, positive $\Delta\mu$ values indicate that the excited dipole moments (μ_E) of all the dyes under study are higher in magnitudes compared to their ground states (μ_G). The increase in dipole moment on excitation may be evidenced the presence of ICT transition²⁰.

Conclusions

The LMRA study of the expression of absorption peak maxima with different solvent parameters (eq. (1)) reveals that the interactions of the dyes under study with solvents in solution are mainly guided by the permanent dipole (dyes)-dipole (solvent) and H-bonding interactions. The similar study of Kamlet-Taft equation for the dyes aid to make conclusion that the positive values of coefficients of ' α ' (HBD) acidity parameter along with solute-solvent dipole-dipole interactions (π^*) guide to the hypsochromic shift of wave numbers for the dyes 1-3. Whereas the negative values of the coefficients of ' β ' (HBA) acidity works in opposite direction on the values of wave numbers shift for these dyes. At the same time, both the negative values of s and b coefficients of the dye 4 indi-

cate that there is bathochromic shift with increasing solvent polarity/dipolarizability and solvent hydrogen bond basicity. The studies of Lippert-Mataga and Reichardt-Ravi plots of Stokes shift also reveal that the permanent dipole (dyes)-dipole (solvent) and H-bonding interactions lead to the spectral shift of the dyes in different solvents. The calculated change in dipole moments for the dyes 1-3 follows in the order : Dye-2 > Dye-3 > Dye-1.

Experimental

All chemicals purchased from Merck, Aldrich, and Himedia were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. All solvents used for synthesis and spectroscopic studies were of spectroscopic grade and found to be transparent and non-fluorescent in the range of excitation and fluorescence emission. 1,3-Dimethyl-6-aminouracil and its azo-derivatives 1,3-dimethyl-5-(aryloxy)-6-aminouracil (1-4, Scheme 1) were synthesized by following the reported method⁸. The absorption and fluorescent spectra were determined in different pure organic solvents on a Shimadzu UV-Vis-1800 spectrophotometer and Perkin spectrofluorometer LS55, respectively. Quartz cuvettes were used for measurements in solution. All the measurements were carried out at room temperature keeping dye concentration as $(1.0-1.02) \times 10^{-5}$ M. Linear Multiple Regression Analysis (LMRA) were performed using Minitab 16 software program.

Regression analysis calculation of empirical solvent parameters :

The absorption peak maximum of each of the azo-dyes (1-4, Scheme 1) under study is vulnerable to shift in either ways in different solvents ranges from non-polar to polar aprotic to polar protic⁸. Absorption maxima data of the dyes reported earlier along with few more data collected from other solvents in this study were considered for regression analysis. The absorption peak maxima Y (ν_{\max} , cm^{-1}) of a dye in different solvents can be expressed as a linear function of different solvent parameters (X_n), as given in eq. (1).

$$Y = a_0 + a_1X_1 + a_2X_2 + a_3X_3 + \dots + a_nX_n \quad (1)$$

This multi-parameter empirical eq. (1) has been developed for the evaluation of solvent effects upon dissolution of a solute. By applying LMRA technique the values of intercept coefficients, a_n ($n = 0-n$) could be determined. The regression intercept ' a_0 ' has been considered as the peak position in the gas phase spectra. The independent variable X_n ($n = 1$ to n) are the solvent interaction parameters which are symbolized as E , K , M , N , J and H reported before²¹. The parameter, ' E ' is the empirical solvent polarity which factors hydrogen bonding and dipolar interactions in between solvent and solute molecules²². The dielectric function ' K ' expresses the dipolar interactions²³. The parameters ' M ' and ' N ' describe the solute permanent dipole-solvent induced dipole and solute permanent dipole-solvent permanent dipole interactions, respectively. The other two parameters ' H ' and ' J ' account for non-specific solute-solvent interactions, such as dispersion and dipolar effects²⁴. The values of these parameters used for correlation equation are listed in Table S1 (Supplementary data).

Regression analysis of Kamlet-Taft coefficients :

The analysis of Kamlet-Taft equation¹⁵⁻¹⁸ (eq. (2)) for the dyes (1-4) under study in different solvents may guide to separate the influence of non-specific interactions such as electrostatic effects (dipolarity/polarizability) from specific interactions like hydrogen bonding.

$$v_{\max} = v_0 + \alpha\alpha + \beta\beta + \pi\pi^* \quad (2)$$

where v_{\max} and v_0 are the wave numbers (in cm^{-1}) corresponds to the maximum absorption bands of the dyes in pure solvents and in gaseous phase, respectively. The parameter α and β express the solvent hydrogen bond donor (HBD, acidities) and acceptor (HBA, basicities) abilities, respectively whereas π^* is the measure of solvent dipolarity/polarizability. The magnitudes of these constants have also been evaluated by LMRA technique. The solvatochromic parameters used for the calculation are listed in Table S2.

Estimation of change in dipole moment ($\Delta\mu$) :

Two quite different methods have been adopted for the calculations of $\Delta\mu$ values of the dyes under study. First method involving Lippert-Mataga expression²⁵ is given in eq. (3).

$$\bar{\nu}_{\text{abs}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{fluo}} = \frac{2(\mu_E - \mu_G)^2}{hca^3} \left[\frac{\epsilon - 1}{2\epsilon + 1} \frac{n^2 - 1}{2n^2 + 1} \right] + \text{constant} \quad (3)$$

where ν_{abs} and ν_{fluo} are absorption and fluorescence maxima wave numbers in cm^{-1} , respectively. The other symbols are bearing usual meanings. The change in dipole moment $\Delta\mu$ ($= \mu_E - \mu_G$) can be evaluated from the slope (S_{LM}) of stokes versus orientation polarizability, Δf [$= \{(\epsilon - 1)/(2\epsilon + 1)\} - \{(n^2 - 1)/(2n^2 + 1)\}$] plot and is expressed by the following eq. (4).

$$\Delta\mu = \left(\frac{S_{\text{LM}}}{2} hca^3 \right)^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where the symbols h and c are bearing usual meanings. ' a ' is denoted as Onsager radius of a solute. The eq. (3) is formulated in such a way that not considering the polarizability, hydrogen bonding effect, complex formation and solvation of the molecules of a solute with solvent molecules rather it would account for the effect of dipole moments induced in the solvent molecules resulting by the excited fluorophore. Thus, for better understanding the effects of these parameters on spectral characteristics, second method involving Reichardt-Ravi correlation expression, as given in eq. (5) for the spectral shifts with molecular-macroscopic solvent polarity parameter, E_{T}^{N} was analyzed^{22,26}. The equation includes not only solvent polarity but also protic hydrogen bonding effect. Where $\Delta\mu_{\text{B}}$ and a_{B} are dipole moment changes on excitation

$$\bar{\nu}_{\text{abs}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{fluo}} = 11307.6 \left[\left(\frac{\Delta\mu}{\Delta\mu_{\text{B}}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{a_{\text{B}}}{a} \right)^3 \right] E_{\text{T}}^{\text{N}} + \text{constant} \quad (5)$$

and Onsager cavity radius, respectively of a betaine dye, and $\Delta\mu$ and ' a ' are the corresponding quantities for the dyes of interest. The change in dipole moment $\Delta\mu$ ($= \mu_E - \mu_G$) can be evaluated from the slope (S_{RR}) of stokes versus E_{T}^{N} plot and is expressed by the following eq. (6).

$$\Delta\mu = \sqrt{\frac{S_{\text{RR}} \cdot 81}{\left(\frac{6.2}{a} \right)^3 11307.6}} \quad (6)$$

The Onsager radius (a) of a solute molecule is calculated by the formula given as below (eq. (7)). Where M is the molecular weight of the solute; ρ is the density of the solute;

$$a = (3M/4\pi\rho N)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

N is the Avogadro's number. The density of the dye 1 is drafted from its crystal analysis data⁸ and the same is

approximated for other dyes, 2-4. The calculated value of 'a' for the dyes is 4.17 Å. Calculated values of Lippert-Mataga solvent polarity functions²⁵ Δf and Reichardt-Ravi solvent parameter (E_T^N)^{22,26} for various solvents are given in Table S3.

Supplementary data

The solvent interaction parameters which are symbolized as E , K , M , N , J and H and the Kamlet-Taft solvatochromic parameters are listed in Table S1 and Table S2, respectively. Calculated values of Lippert-Mataga solvent polarity functions (Δf) and Reichardt-Ravi solvent parameter (E_T^N) for various solvents are given in Table S3. The UV-Vis absorption spectra of the dyes in selective solvents are given in Figs. S1 and S2. The results of regression analysis are given in Tables S4-S11.

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